

NATIONAL WILDLIFE HEALTH CENTER

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DIAGNOSTIC SERVICES CASE REPORT

Final Report

6/11/2020

Case: 29661
Epi/WID #: 200526

Legal Declassified INV#:

Submitter:
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Austin, TX 78744

Date Submitted: 5/27/2020

Specimen description/Identification/Location:

ACC	SPECIES	SPECIMEN TYPE	BAND NUMBER	SUBMITTER'S ID	COUNTY	STATE
001	Snake, Plain-Bellied Water	CARCASS			Williamson	TX

Diagnosis:
Snake Fungal Disease

Event History:
One plain-bellied water snake (*Nerodia erythrogaster*) was found at a duck pond in Shirley McDonald Park in Round Rock, Texas. It had ulcers on the anterior surface and dermatitis on the dorsum and venter. It was collected on 5/14/20 and euthanized (1.0 mL Pentobarbital). Snake Fungal Disease has not been confirmed in this county.

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Comment:

COMMENTS:

The skin lesions present in this Plain-bellied Water Snake are due to Snake Fungal Disease. Fungal organisms with morphology consistent with that of *Ophidiomyces ophiodiicola* (O.o.), the fungus that causes Snake Fungal Disease, are present in the epidermis at lesion sites. Infection with O.o is confirmed by PCR from skin swabs.

WILDLIFE AND DOMESTIC ANIMAL SIGNIFICANCE: Snake Fungal Disease (SFD) is a newly-described deep fungal infection of snakes. Investigations are underway to determine whether the fungus *Ophidiomyces ophiodiicola* is the sole cause of SFD or whether it is caused by multiple pathogens. Examinations of snakes with SFD indicate that the fungus invades deeply into the epidermis and dermis, hence molting may not rid the animal of infection despite temporary resolution of clinical signs. The significance of SFD in free-ranging snakes is also currently under investigation. As the name of the disease implies, SFD is only known to affect snakes.

HUMAN HEALTH CONSIDERATIONS: None

DISEASE CONTROL AND BIOSECURITY: Wear clean disposable gloves when handling sick or dead snakes. Clean supplies and field equipment with soap and water followed by disinfection with a 10% bleach solution (9 part water, 1 part bleach) between animals and sites. When SFD is already known to occur in a region, snakes whose skin lesions appear to resolve with supportive care and/or antifungal therapy may be candidates for release at their capture site, but these individuals should not be released in an area where the disease has not been previously as it is not known if treated snakes may still harbor viable fungus.

Please continue to monitor this mortality event and provide periodic updates to NWHC Epidemiology Team throughout the course of the event as additional considerations and further investigation may be warranted.

GROSS, MICROSCOPIC AND DIAGNOSTIC FINDINGS:

ACCESSION 001

GROSS FINDINGS:

External examination: An immature male Plain-bellied Water Snake in excellent body condition and good post-mortem state is presented for necropsy. The total length is 98 cm and the snout-to-vent length is 83 cm. A 2 x 0.7 cm area of skin ulceration is present on the dorsum right behind the head; a second dorsal ulcer that measures 1.5 x 0.2 cm is present 56 cm distal to the snout. Several other, smaller ulcerated foci are present on the ventrum. Ulcerated skin is reddened, and the surface adjacent to most ulcerated areas is yellow to brown and crusty. The right eye is covered with thick grey material, and flaking skin is present on the lower rostral lip.

Internal examination: There is abundant subcutaneous and visceral fat. The stomach is empty. Immature testes are present.

MICROSCOPIC FINDINGS:

There are multiple foci of necrosis within the epidermis. Necrotic foci are infiltrated by granulocytes. Within these foci are many PAS positive fungal organisms. Morphology of the fungi is consistent with that of *Ophidiomyces ophiodiicola*: the fungi are straight and non-branching, septate, with parallel walls, and are approximately 2 um wide. Cross-sections of several nematode parasites are present in the subserosa of the stomach; there is no associated inflammation or tissue destruction. No significant abnormalities are present in the liver, kidney, pancreas, intestine, spleen, or testes.

DIAGNOSTIC TEST RESULTS

Microbiology: Skin swabs from the dorsum and ventrum are PCR positive for *Ophidiomyces ophiodiicola*.

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The USGS-National Wildlife Health Center conducts wildlife disease investigations with state, federal and tribal partners, and we welcome collaborative dissemination of this information (e.g., publication, press release, technical report, etc.). Please contact the pathologist or wildlife disease epidemiologist assigned to this case to ensure that information is accurately interpreted and appropriately credited.

Copies To:

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CLAYTON WOLF

Texas Parks & Wildlife/Austin, 4200 Smith School Road, Austin, TX 78744

This is a Report for your submission to the National Wildlife Health Center.

For consultation regarding diagnostic findings or laboratory testing and results, please contact the pathologist. Contact information can be found underneath the signature line on this report.

For consultation on the significance of this disease to wildlife populations in your area, assistance with disease control and response, or to report field updates (numbers and species affected, geographical distribution, end date, etc.), please contact an NWHC epidemiologist at NWHC-epi@usgs.gov or 608-270-2480.